

SUSTAINING CITIES, NATURALLY

Urban ecosystem restoration in Europe, China and Latin America

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The economics of nature-based solutions and restoration

 CLEARINGHOUSE 中欧城市森林应对方案	<p>Mayor, B., Toxopeus, H., McQuaid, S., et al., 2021. State of the art and latest advances in exploring business models for nature-based solutions. Sustainability. 13, 1–21. DOI: 10.3390/su13137413</p>
	<p>McQuaid, S., Kooijman, E., Rizzi, D., et al., 2022. The vital role of Nature-Based Solutions in a nature positive economy. Bruxelles. DOI: 10.2777/307761</p>
	<p>Panduro, T.E., Nainggolan, D., Taylor, T., Zandersen, M., 2021. Cost-effectiveness of NBS in the Urban environment. Deliverable 2.3. REGREEN. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7308360</p>
	<p>Kozak, D., Henderson, H., de Castro Mazarro, A., et al., 2020. Blue-green infrastructure (BGI) in dense urban watersheds. The case of the Medrano stream basin (MSB) in Buenos Aires. Sustainability, 12(6), p.2163. DOI: 10.3390/su12062163</p>
	<p>Wild, T.C., Henneberry, J. and Gill, L., 2017. Comprehending the multiple 'values' of green infrastructure—Valuing nature-based solutions for urban water management from multiple perspectives. Environmental research, 158, pp.179-187. DOI: 10.1016/j.envres.2017.05.043</p>
	<p>Calcagni, Fulvia; Langemeyer, Johannes. 2022, Understanding the relational values between people and nature through the observation of virtual communities. Papers: Regió Metropolitana de Barcelona: Territori, estratègies, planejament, Núm. 64, p. 160-170, https://raco.cat/index.php/PapersIERMB/article/view/402480</p>
	<p>Facing Funding Challenges. How to make Profitable Nature Based Solutions Projects for our Cities. Cities Talk Nature Webinar. 2022. Recording: https://interlace-hub.com/facing-funding-challenges-how-make-profitable-nature-based-solutions-projects-our-cities</p>
 CLEARINGHOUSE 中欧城市森林应对方案	<p>Vianna Mansur, A., McDonald R., Güneralp B., et al., 2021., Nature futures for the urban century: Integrating multiple values into urban management. Environmental Science & Policy, 131, 46-56. DOI: 10.1016/j.envsci.2022.01.013</p>

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Policy, governance and institutional issues

REGREEN NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS	<p>Kirsop-Taylor, N., Russel, D., Jensen, A., 2021. Urban governance and policy mixes for nature-based solutions and integrated water policy. Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning, 0, 1–15. DOI: 10.1080/1523908X.2021.1956309</p>
REGREEN NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS	<p>Kirsop-Taylor N., Russel D., 2022, Agencies navigating the political at the science-to-policy interface for nature-based solutions, Elsevier, Environmental Science and Policy 127 (2022) 303–310, DOI: 10.1016/j.envsci.2021.10.029</p>
REGREEN NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS	<p>Morère, L., Grandin, G., Huart, G., et al., 2021. Les solutions fondées sur la nature. Défis et opportunités pour la méga région parisienne in: Atlas Collaboratif de La Mégarégion Parisienne [En Ligne]. UMR CNRS 6266 IDEES, Université de Rouen Normandie. Rouen, p. 6. DOI: 10.48390/ds8t-j329</p>
REGREEN NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS	<p>Banzhaf, E., Anderson, S., Grandin, G., et al., 2022. Urban-Rural Dependencies and Opportunities to Design Nature-Based Solutions for Resilience in Europe and China. Land 11. DOI: 10.3390/land11040480</p>
CONEXUS	<p>Randrup, T.B., Buijs, A., Konijnendijk, C.C. and Wild, T., 2020. Moving beyond the nature-based solutions discourse: introducing nature-based thinking. Urban Ecosystems, 23(4), pp.919-926. DOI: 10.1007/s11252-020-00964-w</p>
CLEARINGHOUSE 中欧城市森林应对方案	<p>Basnou, C., Pino, J., Davies, C., et al., 2020. Co-design processes to address Nature-Based Solutions and Ecosystem Services demands: the long and winding road towards inclusive urban planning. Frontiers in Sustainable Cities, 2, 572556. DOI: 10.3389/frsc.2020.572556</p>
CLEARINGHOUSE 中欧城市森林应对方案	<p>Roitsch, D., Davies, C., Agata, K., et al., 2021. Governance, institutional and economic frameworks for Urban Forests as Nature-based Solutions (UF-NBS). Deliverable D1.4, CLEARING HOUSE. DOI: 10.5271/zenodo.6832603</p>
CLEARINGHOUSE 中欧城市森林应对方案	<p>Davies, C., Chen, W., Sanesi, G., Laforteza, R., 2021. The European Union roadmap for implementing nature-based solutions: A review. Environmental Science & Policy, 121, 49-67. DOI: 10.1016/j.envsci.2021.03.018</p>

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Social aspects of nature-based solutions and restoration

<p>CONEXUS</p>	<p>van der Jagt, A.P., Buijs, A., Dobbs, C., et al., 2022. An action framework for the participatory assessment of nature-based solutions in cities. <i>Ambio</i>, pp.1-14. DOI: 10.1007/s13280-022-01772-6</p>
<p>INTERLACE RESTORING URBAN ECOSYSTEMS RECUPERANDO ECOSISTEMAS URBANOS</p>	<p>Everyone is necessary! Inclusion of Vulnerable Communities in the Planning and Implementation of NBS. Cities Talk Nature Webinar. 2022. Recording: https://interlace-hub.com/everyone-necessary</p>
<p>INTERLACE RESTORING URBAN ECOSYSTEMS RECUPERANDO ECOSISTEMAS URBANOS</p>	<p>Langemeyer, J., F. Baró, 2021. Nature-based solutions as nodes of green-blue infrastructure networks: A cross-scale, co-creation approach, <i>Nature-Based Solutions</i>, Volume 1, 100006, DOI: 10.1016/j.nbsj.2021.100006</p>
<p>INTERLACE RESTORING URBAN ECOSYSTEMS RECUPERANDO ECOSISTEMAS URBANOS</p>	<p>Calderón-Argelich, A., Benetti, S., Anguelovski, I., J.T. Connolly, Langemeyer, J., Baró, F., 2021. Tracing and building up environmental justice considerations in the urban ecosystem service literature: A systematic review, <i>Landscape and Urban Planning</i>, Volume 214, DOI: 10.1016/j.landurbplan.2021.104130</p>
<p>CLEARINGHOUSE 中欧城市森林应对方案</p>	<p>Scheuer, S., Haase, D., Haase, A. et al., 2021. A glimpse into the future of exposure and vulnerabilities in cities? Modelling of residential location choice of urban population with random forest. <i>Natural Hazards and Earth Systems Sciences</i>, 21(1), 203-217. DOI: 10.5194/nhess-21-203-2021</p>
<p>CLEARINGHOUSE 中欧城市森林应对方案</p>	<p>Barber, A., Haase, D., Wolff, M., 2021. Permeability of the city – Physical barriers of and in urban green spaces in the city of Halle, Germany. <i>Ecological Indicators</i>, 125, 107555. DOI: 10.1016/j.ecolind.2021.107555</p>
<p>CLEARINGHOUSE 中欧城市森林应对方案</p>	<p>Haase, D., Wolff, M., Schumacher, N., 2021. Mapping mental barriers that prevent the use of neighborhood green spaces. <i>Ecology & Society</i>, 26(2), 36. DOI: 10.5751/ES-12675-260416</p>
<p>CLEARINGHOUSE 中欧城市森林应对方案</p>	<p>Kičić, M., Haase, D., Marin, A.M., Vuletić, D., Krajer Ostoić S., 2022. Perceptions of cultural ecosystem services of tree-based green infrastructure: A focus group participatory mapping in Zagreb, Croatia. <i>Urban Forestry & Urban Greening</i>, 78, 127767. DOI: 10.1016/j.ufug.2022.127767</p>

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Education for nature-based solutions	
CONEXUS	Living Fences in Buenos Aires: Improving Quality of Air: Schools educational pilot: https://oppla.eu/casestudy/23347
REGREEN NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS	Hedblom, M., Prévot, A.-C., Grégoire, A., 2022. Science fiction blockbuster movies - A problem or a path to urban greenery? Urban Forestry & Urban Greening. 74, 127661. DOI: 10.1016/j.ufug.2022.127661
REGREEN NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS	Development of citizen-science learning tools for teachers, in French (https://formation.vigienature-ecole.fr/). Translation of VNE protocols to English: https://depot.vigienature-ecole.fr/ressources/livrets_anglais/Livret_VNE_English.pdf
REGREEN NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS	REGREEN Podcast Citizen-science at schools & REGREEN podcast Kids and nature learning - how young people can be involved in the regreening of our cities (2 French students involved in REGREEN program): https://www.regreen-project.eu/regreen-podcast/
REGREEN NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS	Observation as a Nature-based Solution (Simon Bénateau, MNHN) Exploring Nature-Based Solutions in Your Classroom MOOC, Scientix https://www.europeanschoolnetacademy.eu/courses/course-v1:Scientix+NBS+2021/about
CLEARINGHOUSE 中欧城市森林应对方案	de Kezel, T., Kilpi, K., Rueda, G., Castaneda, R., 2021. City of Trees. Inspiration and activities to teach about the importance of urban trees and forests. CLEARING HOUSE D5.3. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6834911 . http://clearinghouseproject.eu/city-of-trees/ (English, Mandarin, Catalin, Italian, Spanish, Dutch).

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Environmental aspects of nature-based solutions and restoration

REGREEN NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS	Baker, H.J., Hutchins, M.G., Miller, J.D., 2021. How robust is the evidence for beneficial hydrological effects of urban tree planting? Hydrological Sciences Journal. DOI: 10.1080/02626667.2021.1922692
REGREEN NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS	Jones, L., Reis, S., Hutchins, M., et al., 2022. Airsheds, watersheds and more – The flows that drive intra-extra-urban connections, and their implications for nature-based solutions (NBS). Nature-Based Solutions. 2, 100040. Doi: 10.1016/J.NBSJ.2022.100040
REGREEN NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS	Elze, S., Banzhaf, E., 2022. High-precision monitoring of urban structures to understand changes in multiple ecosystem services. Urban Forestry & Urban Greening. 73, 127616. DOI: 10.1016/J.UFUG.2022.127616
REGREEN NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS	Bird, D.N., Banzhaf, E., Knopp, J., et al., 2022. Combining Spatial and Temporal Data to Create a Fine - Resolution Daily Urban Air Temperature Product from Remote Sensing Land Surface Temperature (LST) Data. Atmosphere. 13, 19. DOI: 10.3390/atmos13071152
REGREEN NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS	Wu, W. Ben, Ma, J., et al., 2021. Spatio-temporal changes in urban green space in 107 Chinese cities (1990–2019): The role of economic drivers and policy. International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation. 103, 102525. DOI: 10.1016/j.jag.2021.102525
REGREEN NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS	Wu, W.-B., Yu, Z.-W., et al., 2022. Quantifying the influence of 2D and 3D urban morphology on the thermal environment across climatic zones. DOI: 10.1016/j.landurbplan.2022.104499
REGREEN NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS	Banzhaf, E., Wu, W., Luo, X., Knopp, J., 2021. Integrated Mapping of Spatial Urban Dynamics—A European-Chinese Exploration. Part 1—Methodology for Automatic Land Cover Classification Tailored towards Spatial Allocation of Ecosystem Services Features. Remote Sensing. 13, 1744. DOI: 10.3390/RS13091744
REGREEN NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS	Wu, W., Luo, X., Knopp, J., Jones, L., 2022. A European-Chinese Exploration : Part 2 – Urban Ecosystem Service Patterns, Processes, and Contributions to Environmental Equity under Different Scenarios. Remote Sensing. 14, 26. DOI: 10.3390/rs14143488
REGREEN NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS	Fletcher, D., Zhao, B., Grandin, G., et al., 2020. Report on assessment of drivers and pressures leading to urban challenges, across the ULLs, including spatial and temporal components. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7308435
INTERLACE RESTORING URBAN ECOSYSTEMS RECUPERANDO ECOSISTEMAS URBANOS	Baró, F. and Maestre-Andrés, S., 2022. El paper de la infraestructura verda metropolitana en relació a la qualitat de l'aire i la mitigació i adaptació al canvi climàtic. Papers: Regió Metropolitana de Barcelona: Territori, estratègies, planejament, Núm. 64, p. 119-129, Download .
CLEARINGHOUSE 中欧城市森林应对方案	Jiali, J., Sheppard S.R.J., Baoquan J., Cheng W., 2021. Planning to Practice: Impacts of Large-Scale and Rapid Urban Afforestation on Greenspace Patterns in the Beijing Plain Area. Forest, 12(3), 316. DOI: 10.3390/f12030316
CLEARINGHOUSE 中欧城市森林应对方案	Haase, D., Hellwig, R., 2022. Effects of heat and drought stress on the health status of six urban street tree species in Leipzig, Germany. Trees, Forests and People, 8, 100252. DOI: 10.1016/j.tfp.2022.100252
CLEARINGHOUSE 中欧城市森林应对方案	Caiyan, W., Junxiang L., Chunfang W., et al., 2021. Estimating the Cooling Effect of Pocket Green Space in High Density Urban Areas in Shanghai, China. Frontiers in Environmental Science, 181. DOI: 10.3389/fenvs.2021.657969

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Ecological quality of restoration activities and nature-based solutions

Miyahara, A.A.L., Wild, T., Sandre, A.A., et al., 2022. **Developing and classifying urban biomes as a basis for nature-based solutions.** Urban Climate, 45, 101251.
[DOI: 10.1016/j.uclim.2022.101251](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.uclim.2022.101251)

Flowing Towards Knowledge. **River Restoration and Revitalization in Latin American and European Cities.** Cities Talk Nature Webinar. 2022. Recording: <https://interlace-hub.com/flowing-towards-knowledge-river-restoration-and-revitalization-latin-american-and-european-cities>

Grandin, G., Deboeuf De los Rios, G., Marc, B., 2022. **Guidelines for a “depaving” and “regreening” strategy in cities.** D3.2 REGREEN.
[DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7308389](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7308389)

Ecological management : Let's bring biodiversity to cities.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LLj8Cl8RoS0>

Nature-based solutions for climate change mitigation and adaptation in Paris Region.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oAs7B53L-A>

Urbanism, architecture and biodiversity: when nature inspires cities and buildings.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XY3yndaXsUU>

Ecosystem services : Biodiversity and nature provide countless benefits for humans.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YbyxzGbYQBc>

Agriculture and biodiversity, growing with nature.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MkhMkKlppZQ>

Andersson, E., Haase, D., Anderson P., et al., 2021. **What are the traits of a social-ecological system: Towards a framework in support of urban sustainability.** Nature Urban Sustainability, 1, 14. [DOI: 10.1038/s42949-020-00008-4](https://doi.org/10.1038/s42949-020-00008-4)

Kronenberg, J., Andersson., E., Barton, D.N. et al., 2021. **The thorny path toward greening: unintended consequences, trade-offs, and constraints in green and blue infrastructure planning, implementation, and management.** Ecology & Society, 26(2), 36. [DOI: 10.5751/ES-12445-260236](https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-12445-260236)

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Other topics

<p>INTERLACE RESTORING URBAN ECOSYSTEMS RECUPERANDO ECOSISTEMAS URBANOS</p>	<p>Introduction to the Agile Workflow. Video: https://youtu.be/hox1GOQ7R24</p>
<p>INTERLACE RESTORING URBAN ECOSYSTEMS RECUPERANDO ECOSISTEMAS URBANOS</p>	<p>Kleeschulte, Marie (2022). Cookbook on virtual exchange formats for cities. INTERLACE Deliverable 4.2. (English/Spanish). https://interlace-project.eu/node/205</p>
<p>INTERLACE RESTORING URBAN ECOSYSTEMS RECUPERANDO ECOSISTEMAS URBANOS</p>	<p>Melo, I. et al. (2021). Categorized database of good practice tools for the design, implementation, monitoring and maintenance of restorative nature-based solutions. INTERLACE Deliverable 3.1. https://interlace-project.eu/node/208</p>
<p>INTERLACE RESTORING URBAN ECOSYSTEMS RECUPERANDO ECOSISTEMAS URBANOS</p>	<p>A playful introduction to restorative nature-based solutions in Latin American and European cities. Cities Talk Nature Webinar. 2021. Recording: https://interlace-hub.com/playful-introduction-restorative-nature-based-solutions-latin-american-and-european-cities</p>
<p>CLEARINGHOUSE 中欧城市森林应对方案</p>	<p>von Döhren, P. & Haase, D., 2022. Geospatial assessment of urban ecosystem disservices: An example of poisonous urban trees in Berlin, Germany. Urban Forestry & Urban Greening, 67, 127440. DOI: 10.1016/j.ufug.2021.127440</p>
<p>CLEARINGHOUSE 中欧城市森林应对方案</p>	<p>Scheuer, S., Jache, J., Kičić, M., Welmann, T., Wolff, M., Haase, D., 2022. A trait-based typification of urban forests as nature-based solutions. Urban Forestry & Urban Greening, 78, 127780. DOI: 10.1016/j.ufug.2022.127780</p>